

THE MEDIATION ROLE OF FEAR OF MISSING OUT (FOMO) ON THE INFLUENCE OF TWIN DATE AND SHOPPING LIFESTYLE ON IMPULSIVE BUYING OF GENERATION Z SHOPEE USERS IN PALU CITY

Muh Fajar Muzakir¹, Ponirin², Syamsul Bahri Dg. Parani³, Asriadi⁴

Universitas Tadulako, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Palu, Indonesia

Email: m.fajarmusdar@gmail.com¹, ppaidjan@gmail.com², syamsulbahridgparani@gmail.com³,
asriadi@untad.ac.id⁴

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Abstract

This study analyzes the influence of Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying with Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) acting as a mediating variable in Generation Z Shopee users in Palu City. The research approach uses a quantitative method with Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) analysis of 100 respondents who meet the criteria of Generation Z (born 1997-2012) who have made transactions at least twice on Shopee and live in Palu City. The results show that both Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle have a positive and significant influence on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) and Impulsive Buying. In addition, by mediating Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) partially complementing both paths. This finding indicates that the Twin Date promotion strategy and shopping lifestyle strengthen consumers' emotional drives, so that e-commerce platforms such as Shopee can utilize it to increase spontaneous sales in Generation Z.

Keywords: *Twin Date, Shopping Lifestyle, Fear of Missing Out (Fomo), Impulsive Buying.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology has dramatically changed consumer shopping patterns in Indonesia. Technological advancements have transformed various aspects of life, including the way people conduct transactions and interact, in line with the progress of digitalization that has also changed consumption patterns across various social groups (Evrianti et al., 2025; Rombe et al., 2021). Previously, purchasing activities were often carried out conventionally through direct visits to physical stores, where consumers could inspect products face-to-face (Muzakir et al., 2021). However, advances in information technology and increasingly widespread internet penetration have encouraged consumers to shift to e-commerce platforms as the primary channel for transactions. According to (Dewi, 2024), e-commerce platforms not only provide consumers with convenience in accessing products without having to visit stores, but also offer advantages such as time efficiency, ease of access, and attractive promotions that are difficult to find in offline transactions. The shift from in-person shopping to online shopping is a clear example of how technology simplifies daily routines (Adhe Istiana Ikramawati et al., 2023). E-commerce is not just about buying and selling products online, but also includes a more comprehensive series of processes, from product development, sales, marketing, delivery, to customer service.

Among the various e-commerce platforms available, Shopee became the top e-commerce platform in Indonesia throughout the first quarter of 2025. According to Ridwan's data (2025), Shopee has: 43% Platform Traffic Share. One of Shopee's effective promotional strategies is the sales campaign on twin dates such as 9.9, 10.10, 11.11, and 12.12. This campaign provides various attractive offers such as big discounts, free shipping, limited-time flash sales, and exclusive vouchers that are only valid during the promotional period. According to Rosa et al (2024) In 2020, the Twin Date Festival experienced a 66 percent increase in sales in August during the "8.8" promotion. According to Kadoena et al. (2024), this type of promotional strategy can encourage impulse purchases, especially among Generation Z, who tend to be responsive to promotions with elements of urgency and visual appeal. According to Aziz et al. (2025), promotions containing elements of urgency can increase consumers' urge to make spontaneous purchases. Generation Z, born between 1997 and 2012, is the first group to access smartphones, social media, and other technologies from an early age, often categorized as digital natives because they grew up in an era of rapid advancements in information technology and social media (Dewi, 2024). The shift in consumer purchasing behavior

from conventional purchasing orientation to online purchasing requires marketers to deeply understand consumer behavior, especially the influence of emotions and internet addiction in driving impulsive buying in the digital commerce (e-commerce) environment, especially in specific segment groups such as Generation Z (Asriadi et al., 2025) . Faced with Twin Date sales offers that give the impression of being limited and urgent, individuals in Generation Z tend to make spontaneous purchases without going through an in-depth planning process. Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) plays a very important mediating variable in explaining how Twin Date promotions and Shopping Lifestyle influence Impulsive Buying in Generation Z Shopee users, because it creates psychological pressure. Psychological factors such as the fear of missing out (Fomo) and the search for immediate emotional satisfaction are the main motivators in impulsive purchases (Putri et al., 2025; Salwanisa and Fitriyah, 2024) . According to Akib et al. (2025), Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) plays a dominant role in driving consumption behavior among Generation Z.

In addition to promotional factors, shopping lifestyle also plays a significant role in shaping impulsive buying behavior. With the rapid advancement of science and technology in the current digital era, human lifestyles are changing, particularly in terms of choosing needs, creating a wider diversity in daily consumption patterns (Nurhaliza et al. 2023) . This lifestyle is not merely seen as fulfilling needs, but also as a means of entertainment, part of social trends, and a medium for consumer self-expression. According to Fadhilah et al. (2025), individuals with a high shopping lifestyle have a greater tendency to make unplanned purchases, especially for fashion products that are very popular on Shopee. When this lifestyle interacts with major promotional momentum such as Twin Date sales, the potential for unplanned purchases increases due to the combination of social needs and limited promotional opportunities. According to Rahayu et al. (2024) , consumers with intense shopping habits tend to make purchases more often without prior planning.

This phenomenon is an interesting focus for research in Palu City, because Generation Z is Shopee's main consumer group with 69.9% of platform usage, who tend to actively shop online due to advances in technology and social media (Prabawanti et al., 2024) . By examining the influence of Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying in Generation Z Shopee users in Palu City, this study aims to provide theoretical contributions in the development of consumer behavior science as well as practical implications for more effective and targeted digital marketing strategies and also this study aims to explore the mediating role of Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) in the relationship between Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying. This research has significance in helping business actors design marketing approaches that not only attract buying interest, but also build consumer loyalty and satisfaction in a sustainable manner. In addition, this study is expected to fill the research gap related to consumer behavior in developing areas such as Palu City, thereby providing in-depth insights for all parties in the e-commerce industry. understand and assist marketers in designing more effective strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Twin Date

Twin Date is a marketing strategy that utilizes the opportunity of dates and months with double digits, for example 4.4 or 5.5, as a special time to offer attractive discounts and promotions through e-commerce platforms, especially Shopee, which is known for its large discounts (Abdiya et al., 2025) . This promotion is routinely anticipated every month, such as the 4th of April, especially by consumers who shop online (Kadoena et al., 2024). Twin Date originated from the Singles Day Sale festival in China, which was first held in 2009. In Indonesia, e-commerce platforms like Shopee have been regularly holding this event since 2019 (Maharani et al., 2022) . Twin Date promotions offer various exclusive, limited-time offers that are only available during the promotional period. According to Tawasuli & Kholifah (2023), consumers receive various attractive offers, such as free shipping coupons that can be used with all payment methods. There are also discount coupons from sellers, flash sales, and cashback coupons in the form of Shopee coins. These offers are designed to increase sales and attract impulse purchases.

Promotions with double dates have a significant influence on impulsive buying behavior among young consumers in South Tangerang (Nurul Eka Putri & Ambardi, 2023) . The results of this study indicate that the younger generation, especially Generation Z, shows a higher response to event-themed promotions, this is closely related to their digital lifestyle which is highly integrated with e-commerce platforms and social media. According to Putra et al. (2024) that promotional messages that are systematically arranged during the double date period not only serve to attract consumer attention but also form a perception of urgency and product limitations, thus triggering consumers to make quick purchasing decisions without going through a deep consideration process.

Shopping Lifestyle

Shopping Lifestyle is a person's actions in spending their time and money where these activities can reflect a person's status, dignity, and habits (Yuangga, 2023) . Lifestyle drives decisions in making purchases not solely driven by basic needs, but also influenced by social, cultural, and psychological factors that influence individual consumption behavior patterns. In the context of online shopping, Generation Z's Shopping Lifestyle is strongly influenced by trends and the desire to "exist" or not be left behind (Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) which encourages them to shop without long consideration (Akib et al., 2025) . Generation Z, growing up in the digital era and Gen Z prefers fast and practical and is easily attracted to various promotions or discounts, so that shopping lifestyle increasingly encourages impulsive buying behavior.

According to Tjemara & Nurlinda. (2025) that shopping lifestyle has an important role in triggering impulsive buying behavior, especially in Fashion products attached to hedonic and symbolic characteristics. Consumers who have a high shopping lifestyle orientation tend to prioritize emotional satisfaction and self-expression, so they are more prone to making spontaneous purchases. According to Papatungan et al., (2021) that product attributes such as quality, design, and promotional offers significantly encourage consumer purchasing intentions in Palu City, especially in technology products that are often part of the daily shopping lifestyle, thus strengthening the role of shopping lifestyle as the main trigger of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) which triggers Impulsive buying behavior in Generation Z. According to Andrean et al. (2024) that shopping lifestyle has a positive and significant influence on the impulsive behavior of Shopee consumers in Garut Regency, where the stronger the tendency of shopping lifestyle, the more likely consumers are to make purchases without prior planning.

Impulsive Buying

Impulsive buying is defined as the process of purchasing goods suddenly and unplanned, often triggered by emotions and moods, often without considering the consequences and prior planning (Ardhi et al., 2024) . According to Pertiwi (2025), impulsive behavior is not only triggered by internal drives but is also influenced by various external factors. By understanding these factors, companies can create more appropriate marketing strategies that align with consumers' mindsets.

Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)

Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is understood as a feeling of anxiety or worry that arises due to the belief that others are enjoying pleasant experiences without one's presence, thus encouraging individuals to stay connected and follow trends continuously (Przybylski et al., 2013) . Generation Z, who grew up in the midst of the digital era, is more susceptible to the influence of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) because of fast access and In-depth understanding of various content, and high affinity with technology and social media (Diana et al., 2026) . In the context of e-commerce, Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) usually arises due to promotional strategies that emphasize urgency, such as flash sales, big discounts, and massive shopping events (Twin Date), which encourage impulsive buying behavior. As a mediating variable, Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) plays an important role in connecting external stimuli such as Twin Date promotions and shopping lifestyles with impulsive buying in Generation Z Shopee users, because it creates an emotional drive that strengthens the desire to buy spontaneously. According to Putri et al. (2025) , the Twin Date promotion positively influences Impulsive Buying through the mediation of Fear of Missing Out (Fomo), namely the fear of missing out on limited discounts that encourage consumers to act quickly without careful planning. According to Wijaningsih et al. (2024), a hedonistic-centered Shopping Lifestyle magnifies the effect through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo), so that e-commerce promotional factors develop into internal psychological pressure that dominates digital consumption behavior.

Framework

Hypothesis

- H1: Twin Date has a positive and significant effect on Impulsive Buying.
- H2: Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant influence on Impulsive Buying.
- H3: Twin Date has a positive and significant effect on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo)
- H4: Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)
- H5: Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) has a positive and significant effect on Impulsive Buying.
- H6: Twin Date has a positive and significant effect on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) as a mediating variable.
- H7: Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) as a mediating variable.

METHOD

The method used in this study is a quantitative method with a descriptive associative type of research. This study utilized primary data obtained by creating a questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1-5 in the form of statements, then distributed to respondents who met the research criteria via the Google Forms platform. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling. sampling method carried out on a population that has certain characteristics or criteria (Sugiyono, 2016) . The qualifications used to determine the respondents of this study are as follows: (1) generation Z born in 1997–2012 (2) have made at least 2 transactions on the Shopee Platform and (3) domiciled in Palu City. This study determined a sample size of 100 generation Z respondents in Palu City who met the research criteria. Because the population nominally cannot be known the exact number, the researcher immediately determined the sample size of 100 respondents in line with the opinion of Copper and Emory quoted in (Rosa et al. 2024) . The data analysis technique used is descriptive analysis, then questionnaire data processing with data quality tests (validity tests, reliability tests), and to test the hypothesis, it was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) program.

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Table 1. Operational Variables

Variables	Indicator	Source
Twin Date	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Attraction of Discounts 2. Attractive Offer 3. Urge to Buy 4. Time Limitation 5. Anticipate Promos 6. Shopping Fun 7. Purchase Plan 8. Purchase Delay 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chandon et al. (2000) 2. Cialdini (2009) 3. Ajzen (1991)
Shopping Lifestyle	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brand Preference 2. Trend Concern 3. Confidence 4. Price comparison 5. Discount Search 6. Quality Evaluation 7. Shopping Efficiency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sproles, G & Kendall, E (1986) 2. Lichtenstein et al. (1993)
Impulsive Buying	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unplanned 2. Without Consideration 3. Promotion Temptation 4. Emotional 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rook & Fisher (1995) 2. Beatty & Ferrell (1998) 3. Verplanken & Herabadi (2001) 4. Bhakat & Muruganantham (2013)
Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trends 2. Discount 3. Regret 4. Promotion 5. Stock 6. Event 7. Comparison 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Przybylski et al. (2013) 2. Hodkinson (2019) 3. Alt (2015) 4. Pittman & Reich (2016)

RESULTS

Validity and Reliability Test

The results of convergent validity testing estimated through outer loading values indicate that all indicators in the Twin Date, Shopping Lifestyle, Impulsive Buying, and Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) constructs have outer loading values that are generally above the recommended minimum limit. As shown in the outer loading table, the majority of indicators show outer loading values ≥ 0.70 , which indicates that each indicator has a good ability to represent the measured latent variables.

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Table 1. Validity test results

Source: smartPLS 4 Report

Figure 1: Outer Loading

Based on Figure 1 above, each indicator can be said to have a significant contribution to the formation of the latent construct in this research model. The results of the reliability test using Cronbach's alpha indicate that all constructs in this study have values exceeding the minimum threshold of 0.70, thus they can be categorized as reliable constructs. As shown in the table, the Twin Date and Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) variables each have Cronbach's alpha values of 0.913 and 0.901, respectively, reflecting a very high level of internal consistency. Meanwhile, the Shopping Lifestyle variable has a value of 0.876, and Impulsive Buying is 0.793, indicating that the indicators in each construct consistently measure the same concept.

Table 1. Reliability test results

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)	0.901	0.916	0.921	0.626
Impulsive Buying	0.793	0.805	0.866	0.618
Shopping Lifestyle	0.876	0.885	0.903	0.572
Twin Date	0.913	0.918	0.929	0.622

Source: smartPLS 4 Report

Based on Table 1 above, the constructs in this research model can be stated to have adequate reliability, so that the results of further analysis including testing of structural relationships and the mediating role of Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) can be interpreted accurately and can be accounted for methodologically.

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Hypothesis Testing

Source: smartPLS 4 Report

Figure 2: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted through a bootstrapping procedure to examine the direct and indirect effects between latent variables, namely Twin Date, Shopping Lifestyle, Fear of Missing Out (Fomo), and Impulsive Buying. The decision-making criteria refer to the path coefficient value > 0.03 and p-value < 0.05, which indicates that the relationship between the variables is positive and statistically significant.

Table 2. Results of the direct effect hypothesis test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Twin Date -> Impulsive Buying	0.274	0.278	0.105	2,610	0.009
Shopping Lifestyle -> Impulsive Buying	0.301	0.300	0.101	2,970	0.003
Twin Date ->Fear of Missing Out (Fomo)	0.326	0.328	0.083	3,942	0,000
Shopping Lifestyle ->Fear of Missing Out (Fomo)	0.381	0.389	0.077	4,971	0,000
Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) -> Impulsive Buying	0.303	0.303	0.104	2,924	0.003

Source: smartPLS 4 Report

a. The Effect of Twin Dates on Impulsive Buying

Based on the results of the structural model test in Table 2, Twin Date is proven to have a positive and significant influence on impulsive buying. This is indicated by a path coefficient of 0.274 with a p-value of 0.009, which is below the 0.05 significance level. Thus, hypothesis H1, which states that Twin Date influences impulsive buying, is accepted. This finding indicates that twin date-based promotions can encourage Generation Z Shopee users in Palu City to make spontaneous purchases without prior planning.

b. The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying

Based on the analysis results in Table 2, shopping lifestyle has a positive and significant influence on impulsive buying, with a path coefficient of 0.301 and a p-value of 0.003. Therefore, hypothesis H2, which states that shopping lifestyle influences impulsive buying, is accepted. These results indicate that a shopping lifestyle that makes shopping a part of daily life contributes to the emergence of impulsive buying behavior.

c. The Effect of Twin Dates on Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)

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Table 2 shows that Twin Date has a positive and significant effect on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo), with a path coefficient value of 0.326 and a p-value of 0.000. This value meets the significance criteria, so the hypothesis H3 which states that Twin Date has an effect on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) is accepted. This finding indicates that twin date promotions can trigger a fear of missing out in consumers, especially Generation Z.

d. The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle on Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)

Based on Table 2, the structural test results show that Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), with a path coefficient value of 0.381 and a p-value of 0.000. These results prove that the hypothesis H4 which states that Shopping Lifestyle has an effect on Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is accepted. This means that the stronger a person's shopping lifestyle, the higher the individual's tendency to experience Fear of Missing Out (FOMO).

e. The Influence of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) on Impulsive Buying

Based on the test results in Table 2, Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is proven to have a positive and significant effect on Impulsive Buying, with a path coefficient value of 0.303 and a p-value of 0.003. Thus, the hypothesis H5 which states that Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) has an effect on Impulsive Buying is accepted. This finding indicates that Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is a psychological factor that plays an important role in driving impulsive buying behavior.

Table 3. Results of the indirect effect hypothesis test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Twin Date -> Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) -> Impulsive Buying	0.099	0.100	0.044	2,246	0.025
Shopping Lifestyle -> Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) -> Impulsive Buying	0.116	0.118	0.047	2,460	0.014

Source: smartPLS 4 Report

f. Indirect Effect (Mediation Test of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO))

The results of the indirect effect test show that Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) has a path coefficient value of 0.116 with a p-value of 0.014, while the Twin Date path on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) has a path coefficient value of 0.099 with a p-value of 0.025. Both paths are statistically significant, so it can be concluded that Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) is able to mediate the effect of Twin Date on Impulsive Buying and mediate the effect of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying so that H6 and H7 of the study are declared accepted.

Coefficient of Determination

The structural model in this study was evaluated by examining the R-square value for the endogenous latent constructs, namely Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) and Impulsive Buying. The R-square value indicates the extent to which the endogenous variables can be explained by the exogenous variables in the research model.

Table 4. The R-square results are shown in the following table:

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)	0.385	0.373
Impulsive Buying	0.537	0.522

Source: smartPLS 4 Report

Based on the test results, the R-square value for the Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) variable is 0.385 with an adjusted R-square value of 0.373. These results indicate that 37.3% of the Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) variable can be explained by the Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle variables, while the remaining 66.7% is explained by other variables outside the research model. The R-square value for the Impulsive Buying variable is 0.537 with an adjusted R-square value of 0.522. This indicates that 52.2% of the Impulsive Buying variable can be explained by the Twin

Date, Shopping Lifestyle, and Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) variables, while the remaining 47.8% is influenced by other factors outside the research model.

DISCUSSION

1. The Effect of Twin Date (X1) on Impulsive Buying (Y)

The effect of Twin Dates on Impulsive Buying occurs because twin date promotions are designed as marketing stimuli based on urgency and time scarcity. Twin Dates don't simply offer discounts, but create time pressure, suggesting that the opportunity is only available for a specific time and won't be repeated anytime soon. For Generation Z, this triggers quick purchasing decisions because they perceive the promotion as a "special moment" that differs from ordinary days. Furthermore, Twin Dates also shape collective expectations. Generation Z doesn't shop individually, but rather within a digital ecosystem full of notifications, countdowns, and the narrative of "everyone is shopping today." These social expectations diminish the rational evaluation process and accelerate the transition from intention to action, leading to spontaneous purchases. Therefore, behaviorally, Twin Dates can encourage impulsive buying without the need for additional psychological intermediaries. The results of this study align with the findings of Aziz et al. (2025) and Putri et al. (2025) who examined impulsive buying behavior during the Shopee Twin Date Promo Event. The study showed that the Twin Date event, which featured significant discounts, flash sales, and a limited duration, significantly increased impulsive buying due to the creation of time pressure and the perception of a rare opportunity.

2. The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle (X2) on Impulsive Buying (Y)

The influence of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying can be explained through changes in consumers' internal attitudes. Shopping Lifestyle represents the extent to which shopping activities become part of lifestyle, entertainment, and self-expression. Generation Z with a high Shopping Lifestyle tends to enjoy browsing, is drawn to product visuals, and views online shopping as a recreational activity, not simply a need-fulfilling activity. In these circumstances, purchasing decisions are not always based on functional needs, but rather on hedonic impulses and momentary emotions. When individuals already have this lifestyle orientation, small stimuli such as discounts or product recommendations are enough to trigger impulsive purchases. Therefore, a shopping lifestyle directly increases the tendency for impulsive buying by reducing cognitive control in the decision-making process. The relationship between shopping lifestyle and impulsive buying is supported by research by Kamali (2024) and Sopiyan & Neny (2020), which states that individuals with a high-shopping lifestyle tend to be more impulsive in making purchasing decisions. This shopping lifestyle causes consumers to view shopping as entertainment, thus weakening cognitive control over spending.

3. The Effect of Twin Date (X1) on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo)(Z)

influence on the Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) arises because the twin date promotion combines two key elements that trigger the Fear of Missing Out (FOMO): time constraints and perceived exclusivity. The Twin Date is communicated as a "once-a-month" event, creating a psychological fear that the opportunity will be lost if not immediately seized. For Generation Z, who are highly connected to social media and digital platforms, Twin Dates are also reinforced by social exposure such as flash sale notifications, product sales figures, and other users' shopping activity. This exposure creates a feeling of being left behind if they don't participate. As a result, Twin Dates serve not only as an economic stimulus but also as a trigger for emotional distress in the form of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO). The influence of Twin Date on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) is in line with research by Wijaningsih et al (2024) which demonstrates that e-commerce promotions on social media increase feelings of Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) through intense exposure to limited-time events. Massively communicated promotions create the perception that the opportunity is important and not to be missed.

4. The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle (X2) on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo)(Z)

The influence of shopping lifestyle on fear of missing out (FOMO) occurs because individuals with a high shopping lifestyle are more sensitive to consumption opportunities. They more frequently monitor promotions, follow trends, and compare themselves to other consumers. This intensity of engagement increases the likelihood of fear of missing out (FOMO) when they perceive a potentially missed opportunity. Furthermore, a shopping lifestyle makes individuals more emotionally attached to shopping activities. When attractive shopping opportunities arise, disengagement is perceived as a psychological loss, not simply a missed discount. Therefore, the stronger a person's

shopping lifestyle, the greater the likelihood of experiencing fear of missing out (FOMO) in response to marketing stimuli.

5. The Influence of Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) (Z) on Impulsive Buying (Y)

The influence of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) on impulsive buying occurs because it functions as a psychological mechanism that suppresses rational decision-making. When individuals experience Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), the primary focus is no longer on the need or benefits of the product, but rather on avoiding regret over missed opportunities. Under the Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) condition, Generation Z tends to make quick decisions to alleviate emotional anxiety. Purchasing becomes a tool to alleviate the fear of missing out, leading to spontaneous and unplanned decisions. Thus, Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) plays a direct role in driving impulsive buying behavior as an emotional response to psychological stress. The influence of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) on Impulsive Buying is supported by research by Asyida & Ahmadi (2025) and Kartika & Bhayangkari (2023), which states that Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) plays a significant role in increasing impulsive buying behavior. Consumers with high levels of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) tend to buy to relieve anxiety due to fear of missing out, rather than out of necessity.

6. The Influence of Twin Date on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) as a Mediating Variable.

The indirect effect of Twin Dates on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) shows that Twin Dates not only directly influence behavior but also generate psychological states that reinforce this effect. Twin Dates create Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) through time constraints and event exclusivity, which then encourages individuals to make impulsive purchases as a way to avoid feeling left out. Because the direct effect of Twin Date on Impulsive Buying remains significant, while the indirect path through Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) is also significant and in the same direction, Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) acts as a complementary partial mediator. This means that Fear of Missing Out (Fomo) is not the only pathway of influence, but serves to strengthen and deepen the impact of Twin Date on impulsive behavior. The mediation of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) in the relationship between Shopping Lifestyle and Impulsive Buying is supported by research by Putri et al. (2025) and Rokhim et al. (2025) who found that Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) strengthens the influence of a consumptive lifestyle on impulsive buying behavior. Individuals with a high Shopping Lifestyle are more likely to experience Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), which then encourages spontaneous buying actions.

7. The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulsive Buying through Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) as a Mediating Variable.

The indirect influence of shopping lifestyle on impulsive buying through fear of missing out (FOMO) occurs because shopping lifestyle creates psychological vulnerability to fear of missing out (FOMO). Individuals with a high-shopping lifestyle are more likely to experience fear of missing out (FOMO) when faced with promotions or current trends, as shopping becomes part of their identity and social activities. Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) then acts as an emotional trigger that transforms lifestyle predisposition into a concrete action in the form of impulsive buying. Similar to the Twin Date pathway, both direct and indirect influences are significant, so Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) acts as a complementary partial mediator that strengthens the relationship between Shopping Lifestyle and impulsive buying behavior.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle have a positive and significant effect on Impulsive Buying among Generation Z Shopee users in Palu City. The Twin Date promotion is able to create time pressure and a perception of exclusivity that encourages consumers to make spontaneous purchases, while Shopping Lifestyle reflects consumers' internal predisposition that makes shopping activities part of their lifestyle and entertainment. In addition, Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle are also proven to have a positive effect on Fear of Missing Out (Fomo), which indicates that urgency-based promotional strategies and the intensity of shopping involvement increase feelings of fear of missing out in consumers. Furthermore, the research results prove that Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) has a positive effect on Impulsive Buying and acts as a complementary partial mediating variable. This means that Twin Date and Shopping Lifestyle not only influence Impulsive Buying directly, but also indirectly through increasing Fear of Missing Out (FOMO). Thus, impulsive buying behavior in Generation Z is the result of the interaction between promotional stimuli, shopping lifestyle, and psychological pressure. Thus, digital marketing

strategies that emphasize urgency and exclusivity are proven effective but have the potential to encourage less planned consumption behavior.

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